

EMERALDS

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Terminology

Terminology	Acronym Description
AI	Artificial Intelligence
API	Application Programming Interface
AT	Analytics Toolbox
DoA	Description of Action
EC	European Commission
ETL	Extract, Transform, Load
FPGA	Field Programmable Gate Array
IP	Internet Protocol
LDS	Location Data Services
MAIaaS	Mobility AI as a Service
ML	Machine Learning
MVT	Map Vector Tile
NIDS	Network Intrusion Detection System
RATEE	Remote Attestation in Trusted Execution Environment
RIA	Research and Innovation Action
SQL	Structured Query Language
TEE	Trusted Execution Environment
UDF	User Defined Functions
UX	User Experience
VPN	Virtual Private Network
WP	Work Package
XAI	Explainable AI

Table 1 – Terminology

Matrix of Alignment

Table 2 outlines the outputs of D2.4 mapped to the GA commitments as stated in the Description of Action (DoA) Annex 1 and Annex 2.

GA Components Title (and type)	GA Component Outline	Document Chapter(s)	Justification
Deliverable			
D2.4 - Demonstration of integrated services (EMERALDS) v1	First integration of EMERALDS tools in CARTO platform environment, testing of the MapVectorTile standard performance in voluminous spatial map plots.	Chapters 2, 3, 4, 5	Results on the integration of EMERALDS tools in the CARTO platform are provided in sections 2,3,4. Results on the testing of the MapVectorTile standard are provided in Chapter 5.
Tasks			
Task 2.2 Deployment of Services and Dashboards	<p>This Task will provide a complete framework of analysis capabilities to perform spatial analytics in SQL, computed natively in the leading cloud data warehouse platforms.</p> <p>CARTO Analytics Toolbox unlocks spatial functions inside cloud data warehouses using an ever-increasing set of User Defined Functions (UDFs) and procedures. These functions allow users to perform spatial analysis natively within the cloud data warehouse environment. Some benefits of that: scalable and serverless spatial analytics; security compliance; and no more ETLs, everything happens within the data warehouse.</p> <p>Furthermore, the task covers all the activities related to implementing a set of AI/ML algorithms and models (that will be developed in the project) into the CARTO platform, to use them for geospatial analysis. EMERALDS will include models and ML analysis into CARTO Analytics Toolbox.</p>	Chapters 2, 3, 4	Chapters 2,3,4 include all EMERALDS toolset core components related to new datatypes and new developments in mobility features for the CARTO platform. Section 3.1 presents an early integration of security tools developed under T2.3 with the CARTO platform, namely "RATEE". Information about the integration plan of the remaining components of Task 2.3 is presented in Table 6.
	Development of dashboards combining different data from CARTO's Data Observatory enables the creation of Mobility Analytics tools for visualizing the results in an interactive environment. This will allow access to non-data science experts through an interactive and scalable web-dashboard.	Chapter 3	Visualisations and dashboards presented on top of the deployment of EMERALDS services in subsections.

Table 2 - Matrix of Alignment

Executive Summary

EMERALDS undertakes the development of an Extreme Scale Urban Mobility Data Analytics as a Service Toolset comprising of reusable tools capable of collecting, processing, analysing and visualizing synchronous and asynchronous batch or stream datasets from multiple heterogeneous resources meantime performing data, AI/ML and DevOps tasks across distributed computing resources covering the entirety of the Computing Continuum. In this direction, a testbed and proof-of-concept environment for the tools, methods, algorithms and software solutions developed in WP3 and WP4, with dedicated DevOps, security and data governance and visual analytics solutions from WP2, is facilitated through the acclaimed CARTO geospatial analytics cloud-native platform. This interaction captures drastically the dynamics of a software development and engineering process in the light of the extreme characteristics of modern mobility data analytics from multiple heterogeneous types of data sources. As a technology integration procedure, the activities within T2.2 pinpoint the as-a service value chain interdependencies in a pragmatic scale of contemporary data science innovation amidst the evolving disruptive data economy ecosystem.

D2.4 entitled “*Demonstration of integrated services (EMERALDS) v1*” is of type “OTHER”, thereby, in addition to the explanations in the text supported by tables and figures, it includes a multitude of technical hyperlinks to other sources. These hyperlinks direct readers to relevant images, code snippets, software code in repositories (such as the [central EMERALDS repo](#)) and additional resources, enhancing the overall understanding and engagement with the content. The deliverable presents the initial incorporation of the tools developed in EMERALDS within the CARTO platform. The collaboration has driven significant innovations within CARTO, leveraging advanced AI and ML algorithms created by EMERALDS to enhance geospatial analysis capabilities, bringing to light the best of both worlds juxtaposing the academic and research world with the industry perspectives. As a result, EMERALDS advancements have led to the development of different components and products in the CARTO platform. Moreover, the competencies of novel standards in storing and encoding geospatial data in vector tiles are explored, laying the ground for EMERALDS standardization outputs. Key standards investigated include the MapboxVectorTiles and GeoParquet standards, with a thorough assessment of their potential in visualising extreme scale geospatial data.

The integration of EMERALDS tools and models into CARTO has enhanced its ability to handle and analyze geospatial data, enabling real-time analysis for immediate insights and informed decision-making. These advanced models democratize access to sophisticated tools, making them accessible without requiring advanced technical expertise. The intuitive solutions provided by EMERALDS lower entry barriers and support a wide range of applications, from urban planning to environmental analysis, thereby improving decision-making across sectors. The integration facilitates the identification of future patterns and trends, enhances planning and response capabilities, and offers more accurate pattern recognition in geospatial data.

Overall, this document provides a comprehensive overview of the developments made by CARTO through its participation in EMERALDS and details on the first integrations of EMERALDS tools, expanding the platform’s capabilities and democratizing access to advanced technologies for more efficient and accurate mobility analytics building on top of cutting-edge geospatial data engineering methods.

1 Introduction

1.1 Purpose and scope of the document

This document serves as a comprehensive overview of the incorporation of EMERALDS tools within the CARTO platform ecosystem. Its primary objective is to outline the integration process of a diverse collection of EMERALDS services, AI algorithms and models, developed in WP3, WP4 and T2.3, into the CARTO platform but also to investigate the deployment options for emeralds services and to introduce a set of visual analytics tool that can be utilized for the development of intuitive dashboards for EMERALDS use cases (T5.2 – T5.4) and Early Adoption Demonstrators (T5.5). The outermost goal of the EMERALDS deployment in CARTO as a prototyping and validation environment is the launch of a novel geospatial intelligence library focused on urban mobility data. On one hand, the introduction of this paradigm needs dilligent adaptations and extension of the CARTO platform base toolkits comprising three core steps: a) Efficient data ingestion and data infrastructure provisions, engaging from testing emeralds with CARTO Data Observatory resources and sophisticated handling of hyperscaler functionalities, b) ameliorating, integrating and enriching the CARTO Analytics Toolbox linked with the Workflows module for intuitive desing of data workflows on the client end c) procurring for reasonable render times for web based dashboards and visualizations synergizing with the CARTO Builder encompassing technologies such as Dynamic Tiling, WebGPU among others. On the other hand, emeralds developers and Toolset integrators provision for making their tools consumable and interfacable with the CARTO platform, ready to plug and play with the demonstration environment and also accomodating the EMERALDS use case business requirements.

The scope of this document encompasses all work carried out in integrating these algorithms and models (emeralds), focusing specifically on their utilization within the CARTO visualization tools (Builder and CARTO Analytics Toolbox) for geospatial analysis purposes. It aims to provide a detailed understanding of how EMERALDS will enhance the CARTO platform by incorporating advanced analytical capabilities.

The deliverable is of type “**OTHER**”, meaning that, in addition to the explanations in the text supported by tables and figures, it includes a multitude of technical hyperlinks. These hyperlinks direct readers to relevant images, s/w developed within the project, code snippets, and additional resources.

This approach allows readers to access detailed explanations, visual aids, and practical examples directly related to the topics discussed, thereby facilitating a deeper comprehension of the material presented. The inclusion of these supplementary resources ensures that readers can explore the content at their own pace and delve into specific areas of interest with ease, making the deliverable not only informative but also user-friendly and adaptable to varying levels of technical expertise. Furthermore, this document highlights the broader significance of integrating analytical tools into the CARTO platform, emphasizing its potential to cater to a wider audience of users.

1.2 Relation to Work Packages, Deliverables and Activities

Work Package 2 (WP2) plays a crucial role in the integration of EMERALDS tools within the CARTO platform ecosystem. WP2 serves as the facilitator backbone for the emeralds services, extending their usability beyond a niche user base of software developers, data scientists and engineers to user bases that can benefit from the services' added value. To this end, a series of integration activities grouped under the EMERALDS 1st Integration Cycle have been carried out (WP2, WP3 ,WP4 and WP5). This integration effort involves close collaboration with several other Work Packages (WPs), namely WP3 and WP4, as well as WP2. Within WP2, TUC has developed the emeralds that are related to security. Additionally, both WP3 and WP4 have contributed to the development of EMERALDS relevant to the project objectives.

The relationships between these WPs are instrumental in achieving our collective goal of integrating the EMERALDS into the CARTO platform for geospatial data visualization purposes. By utilizing the knowledge and inputs from TUC, WP3, and WP4, WP2 aims to facilitate seamless integration and utilization of the developed EMERALDS within CARTO's analytics framework. This collaborative effort underscores the interdisciplinary nature of our project and highlights the importance of cross-WP cooperation in achieving project milestones and deliverables.

Summary of current EMERALD integrations and deployments

Table 3 lists the different emeralds developed within the core EMERALDS research and technical WPs, constituting the EMERALDS toolset offering, that have been streamlined for integration and further deployment in the CARTO platform, and the corresponding sections in this document where the relevant process is described.

Table 3 Deployment and integration of EMERALDS services in CARTO per WP

EMERALDS Research/Technical WP	WP emeralds integrated/ deployed	Section
WP2 Reference Architecture and Toolset Integration	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • FPGA-based Network Intrusion Detection System • Remote Attestation in Trusted Execution Environments 	Section 3.1
WP3 Mobility Data Processing at the Computing Continuum	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mobility/trajectory data compression • Sensor data fusion • Extreme-scale map-matching • Hot-spot analysis 	Sections 2.1, 2.2
WP4 Extreme Scale Mobility Data Analytics & Learning	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Dropoff / Destination Prediction • Monitoring and Forecasting Shared Mobility Demand • Probabilistic Trip Chaining • Trajectory Data Analysis • Real-time Extreme Scale Map Matching • Mobility AI-as-a-Service Features 	Section 2.3

1.3 Contribution to WP2 and Project Objectives

Task 2.2 is set to develop specialized tools for geospatial analytics and location intelligence, building a comprehensive analysis framework for performing spatial analytics in SQL, natively computed in top cloud data warehouse platforms. Following this, combining diverse data from partner data resources, models or other software components into interactive dashboards, creates powerful Mobility Analytics tools. These tools enable non-data science experts to access and interact with complex data through scalable web dashboards. The developed solutions will be tested and validated through pilot use cases (D5.2 – D5.7, M24 and M33) and early adoption applications (D5.8, M36), showcasing their effectiveness in extreme data workflows and contributing to achieving Project Objective 4.

D2.4 directly feeds into the targets set under WP2 and substantiates the necessary methods, tools and processes towards the attainment of Project Objective 1 (O1): **Design a service-oriented reference architecture of a palette of services ('emeralds') for extreme scale urban mobility data analytics**, underpinned by a distributed computing environment that includes edge/fog nodes and cloud nodes, that ensure that both edge and cloud processing contribute towards establishing a robust processing pipeline. The work carried out in T2.2, reported in D2.4 (M18) and D2.5 (M36) focuses on demonstrating the added value and extended functionalities of EMERALDS tools in processing, analysing and visualising complex geospatial information as met in a plethora of urban mobility data driven applications.

In this direction, the CARTO platform serves as a prime testbed for exploring the enhancements and novel capabilities incurred from project's software developments. D2.4 addresses how to make these tools usable within the CARTO platform, thereby increasing their utility and accessibility to a wider range of users. In this regard, WP2 ensures that EMERALDS is user-friendly and accessible to end users, enhancing their impact and integrating them into a comprehensive platform for broader usage.

This deliverable D2.4 release provides the basic connectivity of emeralds and the CARTO platform. The integrations and new modules provide the foundation for realizing the value of Emeralds services for users. Since CARTO is the end user's platform, we will take advantage of delivering, through a simple interface and many capabilities, all the value that EMERALDS offers.

1.4 Structure of the Document

This deliverable is of type OTHER and provides a comprehensive overview of the integration of EMERALDS tools into the CARTO platform, focusing on enhancing urban mobility data analytics. The document is organized into several key sections. It begins with an introduction that outlines the purpose and scope, followed by a discussion of the relation to work packages, deliverables, and project objectives. Chapter 2 details the deployment of services and dashboards, including the integration of EMERALDS into the CARTO Analytics Toolbox, MobilityDB, and AI/ML models. Chapter 3 addresses the security and data governance layer, providing insights into the tools developed to ensure data integrity and protection. Additionally, Chapter 4 includes an analysis of the Map Vector Tile format, comparing it with other formats and technologies. Finally, Chapter 5 concludes with findings, next steps, and detailed technical explanations, code repositories, and practical examples in the annexes.

2 Deployment of Services and Dashboards

2.1 Integration in CARTO Analytics toolbox

In this section, the methodology employed and the results of the matching and identification of EMERALDS services with the highest potential for integration and further deployment within the CARTO platform is presented, broken down to WP level. A detailed functionality and requirements analysis is provided with the respective justifications.

The CARTO Platform is a cloud-native solution designed to operate on modern data warehouses and data lakes, such as BigQuery, Snowflake, and Databricks, among others. For a comprehensive overview of the platform, please refer to Annex 2. A major component of the CARTO Platform is the Analytics Toolbox (AT)—a library offering a suite of tools for spatial analysis within SQL environments. These functions enhance the capabilities of data warehouses with advanced analytical features.

The objective of this task and deliverable is to integrate various EMERALDS services into the Analytics Toolbox, enabling their use directly from SQL consoles or via CARTO Workflows to ultimately provide extreme scale advanced analytical features.

The chosen methodology for this integration aligns with a cross-sector Business Understanding approach, designed to cross-assess and incubate functions, research methods, tools, and algorithms from low Technology Readiness Levels (TRL) to high TRL. It is based on a combination of the Technology Transfer Process¹, Open Innovation² and Research to Market³ frameworks. The identification of the integration potential exercise is particularly suitable for transitioning research-based technologies into industrial applications. The functional analysis also pointed the adjustments needed on the CARTO in-house technology to facilitate the operation of emeralds within the AT.

First, the objectives and scope based on the descriptions of the emeralds from D3.1 and D4.1 were screened and discussed in dedicated cross WP meetings, forming a cross-functional team of EMERALDS academic partners and industry partners. Functional and non-functional requirements of the services, available in D2.1, were assessed and evaluated for their compatibility with CARTO. Open source services code review was conducted and requirements on the platform side clearly elicited. Following this, a dedicated integration plan for the CARTO platform complying with the EMERALDS Toolset Integration Plan presented in D2.2 was devised setting timelines and milestones. During the 1st Integration Cycle regular workshop, standalone technical demos of WP2, WP3 and WP4 were shared between the cross-functional team members and revealed the components with the highest deployment potential. In-house CARTO developments were performed to update the Analytics Toolbox along with implementation of proper interfaces that enable data flows between the CARTO environment and EMERALDS services. The performance of the tested components is then measured (KPIs) and the feedback collected is utilized as a guide for iterations taking place in the 2nd Implementation-Integration Cycle (M20-M33). A comprehensive demonstration showcasing the deployment and integration of services is presented in designated sections, specifically focusing on visualizations within CARTO Dashboards.

2.1.1 New EMERALDS ancillary Routing Service

Taking into account the findings of the innovation screening and assessment, CARTO has introduced a Routing service as part of WP2, enhancing the platform's capability to perform large-scale route optimization and network analysis. The aim is to cater the execution needs and streamline functionalities of the WP3 and WP4 EMERALDS services, strengthening network analytics consistency between the novel software and the CARTO Analytics Toolbox.

The auxiliary service consists of a route engine and networks analytics functions. The route engine is designed to handle complex routing calculations at scale. This includes computing the most efficient paths for various types of transportation, such as vehicles, bicycles, and pedestrians. Integrating the route engine with the existing spatial data capabilities of CARTO and the computational power of BigQuery, provides users with the ability to perform advanced route optimization and network analysis efficiently. In summary the key features offered are :

- **Large-Scale Route Optimization:** The route engine supports large datasets, enabling the optimization of routes for extensive transportation networks. This is particularly useful for logistics companies, urban planners, and public transportation authorities who need to manage and optimize thousands of routes simultaneously.
- **Network Analysis:** Users can analyze the efficiency and performance of their transportation networks. This includes identifying bottlenecks, optimizing traffic flow, and ensuring the most efficient use of resources. Network analysis helps in making data-driven decisions to improve transportation infrastructure and services.
- **Integration with BigQuery:** By leveraging Google BigQuery's powerful data processing capabilities, the route engine can handle complex queries and large datasets with ease. This integration ensures that users can perform route optimization and network analysis without the need for extensive computational resources on their end.
- **Scalability and Efficiency:** The route engine is designed to scale with the needs of the users. Whether it's optimizing a small fleet of vehicles or managing a city-wide public transportation system, the engine provides consistent performance and reliability.

LDS Module in the CARTO Analytics Toolbox

Additionally, the Location Data Services (LDS) module in the CARTO Analytics Toolbox enhances capabilities for spatial analysis and routing. These are the key functions included:

- **CREATE_ISOLINESⁱ:** This function calculates isolines (polygons) from given origins (points) in a table or query. It creates a new table with the columns of the input table or query except the geom_column plus the isolines in the column geom (if the input already contains a geom column, it will be overwritten). The function calculates isolines sequentially in chunks of N rows, N being the optimal batch size for this data warehouse and the specific LDS provider that you are using.

ⁱ https://docs.carto.com/data-and-analysis/analytics-toolbox-for-bigquery/sql-reference/lDS#create_isolines

- **CREATE_ROUTES**ⁱⁱ: This function calculates routes (line strings) between given origins and destinations (points) in a query. It creates a new table with the columns of the input query, including the resulting route in the user-defined column `geom_column` (if the input already contains a column named `geom_column`, it will be overwritten), and a `carto_routing_metadata` column with the response of the service provider except for the route geometry. The function calculates routes sequentially in chunks of 100 rows.
- **ISOLINE**ⁱⁱⁱ: This function calculates the isoline polygon from a given point.

The introduction of the route engine and networks as part of WP2, along with the enhanced LDS module in the CARTO Analytics Toolbox, provide robust solutions for optimizing transportation routes, analyzing network efficiency, and improving overall decision-making in urban planning and logistics. In turn, the development lays the groundwork for leveraging cutting-edge technology delivered by the EMERALDS services to address complex mobility challenges and drive better outcomes in transportation and urban development.

New UDF functions

To render the above mentioned components more user friendly and accessible, a set new user-defined functions (UDFs) designed to empower users to harness temporal and spatial data more effectively have been developed. Below are the key enhancements across different modules.

Routing Module

A routing module that includes the following functions:

- **ROUTING_MATRIX**^{iv}: Calculates origin-destination matrices, enabling users to efficiently analyze travel times and distances between multiple points.
- **ROUTING_ISOLINES**^v: Computes isolines around a set of locations, which is useful for visualizing areas accessible within specific travel times.

Statistic Module

A new set of procedures within the statistics module enables users to create spatial scores (also known as composite indicators or indexes) derived from a combination of different features. These procedures include:

- **CREATE_SPATIAL_COMPOSITE_SUPERVISED**^{vi}: Computes a spatial composite score as the residuals of a regression model, useful for detecting areas of under- and over-prediction.

ⁱⁱ https://docs.carto.com/data-and-analysis/analytics-toolbox-for-bigquery/sql-reference/lDs#create_routes

ⁱⁱⁱ <https://docs.carto.com/data-and-analysis/analytics-toolbox-for-bigquery/sql-reference/lDs#isoline>

^{iv} https://docs.carto.com/data-and-analysis/analytics-toolbox-for-bigquery/sql-reference/routing#routing_matrix

^v https://docs.carto.com/data-and-analysis/analytics-toolbox-for-bigquery/sql-reference/routing#routing_isolines

^{vi} https://docs.carto.com/data-and-analysis/analytics-toolbox-for-bigquery/sql-reference/statistics#create_spatial_composite_supervised

- **CREATE_SPATIAL_COMPOSITE_UNSUPERVISED^{vii}**: Performs an aggregation of individual variables, scaled and weighted accordingly, into a spatial composite score.
- **CRONBACH_ALPHA_COEFFICIENT^{viii}**: Measures the internal consistency of the variables used to derive the spatial composite score.

Additionally, we have added new functions to perform space-time cluster analysis:

- **GETIS_ORD_SPACETIME_QUADBIN^{ix}**: For quadbin indexes.
- **GETIS_ORD_SPACETIME_H3^x**: For H3 indexes.

Classification of Spatio-Temporal Hotspots

This feature enables users to classify the hotspots or coldspots based on their trend and their historical value into different categories. This analysis relies on the output of Spacetime Getis-Ord Gi* statistic and provides a richer output by differentiating hot and coldspots. This classification is especially beneficial for telecommunications companies aiming to optimize their network distribution. By identifying where demand is growing, where it peaks seasonally, or where it is consistently high, telcos can strategically deploy resources to ensure optimal signal quality and service reliability.

Time Series Clustering

This tool allows for the grouping of locations that exhibit similar temporal patterns. This capability is crucial for insurers to fine-tune their financial planning. By recognizing areas with comparable claim timelines, insurers can better forecast claim volumes and allocate budget resources more effectively, whether on an annual or monthly basis. Additionally, this analysis is invaluable for urban mobility and transportation planning. Identifying clusters of locations with similar traffic patterns can aid in optimizing traffic management, public transportation schedules, and infrastructure development to accommodate peak times and enhance overall urban flow.

Support of different Data warehouses

From the infrastructure perspective, deploying novel services entails a need to extend the current interconnections and management operations of various data warehouses supported by CARTO⁴. To this end, external technical links listing all SQL functions tailored for interfacing the Analytics Toolbox with the supported data warehouses are delineated. Therefore the integration of emeralds is streamlined facilitating their effective utilization within the Analytics Toolbox. These functionalities are also useful for the visualization needs of EMERALDS Use Cases (WP5).

^{vii} https://docs.carto.com/data-and-analysis/analytics-toolbox-for-snowflake/sql-reference/statistics#create_spatial_composite_unsupervised

^{viii} https://docs.carto.com/data-and-analysis/analytics-toolbox-for-bigquery/sql-reference/statistics#cronbach_alpha_coefficient

^{ix} https://docs.carto.com/data-and-analysis/analytics-toolbox-for-bigquery/sql-reference/statistics#getis_ord_spacetime_quadbin

^x https://docs.carto.com/data-and-analysis/analytics-toolbox-for-bigquery/sql-reference/statistics#getis_ord_spacetime_h3

Google BigQuery

Below are the functions from the CARTO Analytics Toolbox for BigQuery^{xi}:

- **GENERATE_TRADE_AREAS**: This procedure generates the trade areas for each location specified based on the method and the options provided. Four methods are available: buffer, kring-h3, kring-quadbin and isoline.
- **CREATE_SPATIAL_SCORE**: This procedure allows to derive spatial scores using both point geometries and polygon geometries.
- **CREATE_SPATIAL_PERFORMANCE_SCORE**: Procedure to rank stores or merchants based on a spatial composite score that detects if locations are performing as expected
- **HTTP_REQUEST**: Performs a request to an external URL and returns the results.
- **IMPORT_URL**: Imports a file that is available at a defined URL into a table in the current connection.
- **CREATE_ISOLINES**: Calculates the isolines (polygons) from given origins (points) in a table or query.
- **CREATE_ROUTES**: Calculates the routes (line strings) between given origins and destinations (points) in a query
- **ISOLINE**: Calculates the isoline polygon from a given point.
- **ST_ANGLE**: Finds the angle formed by two adjacent segments defined by 3 points.
- **ST_MINKOWSKIDISTANCE**⁵: Calculate the Minkowski p-norm distance between two features.
- **ST_DELAUNAYLINES**: Calculates the Delaunay triangulation⁶ of the points provided. An array of line strings is returned.
- **ST_DELAUNAYPOLYGONS**: Calculates the Delaunay triangulation of the points provided. An array of polygons is returned.
- **ST_POLYGONIZE**: Creates a set of polygons from geographies that contain lines that represent their edges.
- **ST_VORONOILINES**: Calculates the Voronoi diagram of the points provided⁷. An array of lines is returned.
- **ST_VORONOIPOLYGONS**: Calculates the Voronoi diagram of the points provided. An array of polygons is returned.
- **ROUTING_MATRIX**: This procedure calculates the shortest paths in terms of travel times or distances for all routes between all of a given set of locations.

^{xi} <https://docs.carto.com/data-and-analysis/analytics-toolbox-for-bigquery/sql-reference>

- **ROUTING_ISOLINES:** This procedure generates a table containing isolines in terms of either travel times (isochrones) or distances (isodistances) for a given set of origin locations and range limits to be computed on the road network table.
- **CREATE_SPATIAL_COMPOSITE_SUPERVISED:** This procedure derives a spatial composite score as the residuals of a regression model which is used to detect areas of under- and over-prediction.
- **CREATE_SPATIAL_COMPOSITE_UNSUPERVISED:** This procedure combines (spatial) variables into a meaningful composite score.
- **CRONBACH_ALPHA_COEFFICIENT:** This procedure computes the Cronbach's alpha coefficient for a set of (spatial) variables.
- **GETIS_ORD_SPACETIME_H3_TABLE:** This procedure computes the space temporal Getis-Ord G_i^* statistic for each H3 index and each datetime timestamp
- **GETIS_ORD_SPACETIME_H3:** This table function computes the space temporal Getis-Ord G_i^* statistic for each H3 index and each datetime timestamp
- **GETIS_ORD_SPACETIME_QUADBIN_TABLE:** This procedure computes the space temporal Getis-Ord G_i^* statistic for each Quadbin index and each datetime timestamp
- **GETIS_ORD_SPACETIME_QUADBIN:** This table function computes the space temporal Getis-Ord G_i^* statistic for each Quadbin index and each datetime timestamp

Snowflake

Below are the functions from the CARTO Analytics Toolbox for Snowflake^{xii}:

- **HTTP_REQUEST:** Performs a request to an external URL and returns the results.
- **IMPORT_URL:** Imports a file that is available at a defined URL into a table in the current connection.
- **CREATE_ISOLINES:** Calculates the isolines (polygons) from given origins (points) in a table or query.
- **CREATE_ROUTES:** Calculates the routes (line strings) between given origins and destinations (points) in a query.
- **ISOLINE:** Creates an isoline from the provided origin.
- **ST_MINKOWSKIDISTANCE:** Calculate the Minkowski p-norm distance between two features.

^{xii} <https://docs.carto.com/data-and-analysis/analytics-toolbox-for-snowflake/sql-reference>

- **CREATE_SPATIAL_COMPOSITE_SUPERVISED:** This procedure derives a spatial composite score as the residuals of a regression model which is used to detect areas of under- and over-prediction.
- **CREATE_SPATIAL_COMPOSITE_UNSUPERVISED:** This procedure combines (spatial) variables into a meaningful composite score.
- **CRONBACH_ALPHA_COEFFICIENT:** This procedure computes the Cronbach's alpha coefficient for a set of (spatial) variables.
- **GETIS_ORD_H3:** This procedure computes the Getis-Ord G_i^* statistic for each row in the input table.
- **GETIS_ORD_QUADBIN:** This procedure computes the Getis-Ord G_i^* statistic for each row in the input table.
- **GETIS_ORD_SPACETIME_H3:** This procedure computes the space temporal Getis-Ord G_i^* statistic for each H3 index and each datetime timestamp.
- **GETIS_ORD_SPACETIME_QUADBIN:** This procedure computes the space temporal Getis-Ord G_i^* statistic for each Quadbin index and each datetime timestamp

Amazon Redshift

Below are the functions from the CARTO Analytics Toolbox for Redshift^{xiii}:

- **HTTP_REQUEST:** Performs a request to an external URL and returns the results.
- **IMPORT_URL:** Imports a file that is available at a defined URL into a table in the current connection.
- **CREATE_ISOLINES:** Calculates the isolines (polygons) from given origins (points) in a table or query.
- **CREATE_ROUTES:** Calculates the routes (line strings) between given origins and destinations (points) in a query.
- **ISOLINE:** Calculates the isoline polygon from a given point.
- **GETIS_ORD_QUADBIN:** This function computes the Getis-Ord G_i^* statistic for each Quadbin index in the input array.

PostgreSQL

Below are the functions from the CARTO Analytics Toolbox for PostgreSQL^{xiv}:

^{xiii} <https://docs.carto.com/data-and-analysis/analytics-toolbox-for-redshift/sql-reference>

^{xiv} <https://docs.carto.com/data-and-analysis/analytics-toolbox-for-postgresql/sql-reference>

- **H3_POLYFILL:** Returns an array of H3 cell indexes contained in the given geometry at a given level of detail.
- **QUADBIN_POLYFILL:** Returns an array of quadbin cell indexes contained in the given geometry at a given level of detail.

Databricks

In the next deliverables, we will develop functions relevant to mobility analytics within CARTO Analytics Toolbox for Databricks. Currently, these functions are not available, but they will be included soon with support for Databricks' Photon-accelerated Spatial SQL and Apache Sedona for other Spark clusters.

2.1.1.1 Visualization on CARTO Dashboards

The map below (Figure 2-1) shows the Manhattan Stations catchments areas. It illustrates the areas within <5 min, 5-10 min and >10 min walking distance to each station, and the population within each catchment area is shown.

Figure 2-1: Manhattan Stations catchments areas

The live map on CARTO Builder can be accessed here.^{xv}

The map below (Figure 2-2) shows an example of the public transport trajectory for the city of Riga along with the histogram of the delays predicted. In addition, it shows the average delay per hour per transportation type (bus, tram, trolley).

^{xv} <https://clausa.app.carto.com/map/a1b77473-fb2c-4d0d-a9f0-b3a8e046c185>

Figure 2-2: Riga Public Transports Trajectories and Public transports predicted delays

The map can be accessed here. ^{xvi}

2.1.2 Integration and Connection to MobilityDB

MobilityDB is a core service of the EMERALDS project, enhancing PostgreSQL and PostGIS with advanced mobility data types and functions. In **Mobility Data Fusion and Management (T3.3)**, the services **mobility/trajectory data compression (ULB)**, and **sensor (GPS, GTFS, radar, etc.) data fusion (ULB)**, have been assessed and for their deployment in CARTO potential, showing high technological compatibility with the CARTO Platform and high value adding capabilities, especially due to the SQL manipulation features introduced by the services.

To integrate these services with the CARTO Platform to unlock their functionalities, a new connectivity type to PostgreSQL has been developed. With this new connectivity, it is now possible to establish a connection to a PostgreSQL database and state operational the services upon they perform data operations.

Leveraging the cloud-based hosting of the services on the ATOS Mobility AI-as-a Service platform (T4.3, D4.1) which integrates the T3.3 services for backend operations to accommodate AI model development, training and inference pipelines, an API was set-up between the complete MobilityDB instance and CARTO. Subsequently, a connection was established from the CARTO platform, as illustrated in Figure 2-3 below. This integration enables users to visualize and process the output from EMERALDS components in WP4, as detailed in Table 5, within the CARTO platform.

This seamless connection enhances the capabilities of the CARTO platform, allowing for sophisticated data visualization and processing, thus significantly improving the user experience and analytical capabilities. It also offers a new Data Warehouse Management option to users.

^{xvi} <https://clausa.app.carto.com/map/7f880239-0d1d-488a-aeab-b22eddf9261>

Data warehouse

 PostgreSQL
mobilitydb-emerlads

Your PostgreSQL credentials

📘 CARTO Analytics Toolbox for PostgreSQL
 The Analytics Toolbox provides additional geospatial functions to expand the possibilities of PostgreSQL + PostGIS, such as tileset generation functions or extensive support for quadbin as spatial index. Learn more in our [documentation](#).

Name

Server

Username Password

Database Port

SSL
 Use SSL to encrypt the connection

Permissions and sharing

 Private (default)
 Only you can view and edit
[Manage options](#)

Figure 2-3: ATOS connection from CARTO platform

This functionality is now available on the CARTO platform for use by any user. To test its capabilities, we utilized a tutorial from the MobilityDB GitHub repository (<https://docs.mobilitydb.com/MobilityDB-workshop/master/ch04.html>), replicating a typical analysis scenario (check the previous Figure 2-3).

2.1.2.1 Visualization on CARTO Dashboards

Figure 2-4 showcases the use of MobilityDB within the CARTO platform through the new PostgreSQL connection, using the complete Brussels Public Transport network as a proof of concept for the data management and fusion backend operations, economizing valuable cloud resources and enabling faster map rendering and visual analytics on multiple data resources.

Figure 2-4: Map from MobilityDB replicated in CARTO platform

Map can be accessed here. ^{xvii}

2.2 Integration of emeralds in CARTO Workflows

The beyond-the-state-of-the-art characteristics of EMERALDS services necessitated a series of in-house developments focused on harmonizing their functional and non-functional requirements with CARTO Workflows. These efforts were essential to render the integration process feasible and facilitate the deployment of the services. These in-house developments addressed unique technical challenges, allowing for interoperability, scalability, and advanced functionality across the entire platform. Enriching CARTO Workflows with new components lays the groundwork for establishing User Defined Functions that can accommodate emeralds as well as offering users a visual interface to interact and access both UDFs and emeralds.

Table 4 showcases the deployment and integration progress of WP3 emeralds within CARTO's ecosystem. Detailed deployment methods and repository links provide transparency and accessibility for ongoing development and implementation efforts.

Table 4 Deployment and integration of WP3 emeralds in CARTO per Task

EMERALDS Catalogue	D/I	Means of Deployment/ Integration	Repository Link
Privacy-aware in situ Data Harvesting (T3.1)			
Privacy aware data ingestion (UPRC)	N/A	Not Applicable (edge tier component)	Project's GitHub

^{xvii} <https://clausa.app.carto.com/map/bee90e3e-8507-4b0e-8b2e-52d58f2ff03d>

Extreme-scale stream processing orchestrator (UPRC)	No	Not Applicable (edge tier component, only in the case of CC pipeline where a dataset or task is assigned to higher computing tiers and pushed to a CARTO supported data warehouse)	Project's GitHub
Extreme-scale Cloud/Fog Data Processing (T3.2)			
Extreme-scale map-matching (UPRC)	Planned	Possible integration in Snowflake	Project's GitHub
Weather enrichment (UPRC)	No	Possible integration through BigQuery. Utilized for incorporating weather data into analyses.	Project's GitHub
Spatio-temporal querying (UPRC)	No	Unsupported push or pull.	Project's GitHub
Hot-spot analysis (UPRC)	Planned	Under development, useful for spatial hotspot detection	Under Construction
Mobility Data Fusion and Management (T3.3)			
Mobility/trajectory data compression (ULB)	Yes	MobilityDB has been deployed in CARTO for backend operations. Implemented for reducing data storage requirements	Project's GitHub
Sensor (GPS, GTFS, radar, etc.) data fusion (ULB)	Yes	MobilityDB has been deployed in CARTO for backend operations. Offers capability to combine GPS, GTFS or radar data pushed to CARTO supported data warehouses	Project's GitHub

The EMERALDS-CARTO mapping integration for WP3 focuses on various tasks as can be seen in the table above. For ***Privacy-aware in situ Data Harvesting (T3.1)***, the integration is not feasible due to the fact that the execution domain for these services are edge devices⁸; a separate service could use this emerald to push data to a data warehouse where CARTO is connected. Privacy-aware data ingestion (UPRC, AIT) also has neither direct integration or deployment potential due to similar reasons. The Extreme-scale stream processing orchestrator (UPRC) is not integrated because it is seen as a tool for deployment and is unrelated to CARTO.

For ***Extreme-scale Cloud/Fog Data Processing (T3.2)*** emeralds, the extreme-scale map-matching (UPRC) has possible integration in Snowflake. Weather enrichment (UPRC) is not directly integrated, since it support data warehouse different form the data warehouses connected to CARTO. Spatio-temporal querying (UPRC) also has no integration, but if different systems for querying are exposed as services, they can be used with an API. Hot-spot analysis (UPRC) might be integrated as CARTO already has a space-time get set in the Analytics Toolbox, with new functions to be released by the end of the 2nd integration cycle.

Mobility Data Fusion and Management (T3.3) emeralds include the mobility/trajectory data compression (ULB) service, which has been integrated with CARTO, and Sensor (GPS, GTFS, radar, etc.) data fusion (ULB), which is similarly integrated based on the work presented in section 2.1.2.

CARTO Workflows is a robust tool within the CARTO platform that simplifies and automates spatial data analysis and visualization. Users can create, manage, and share complex geospatial workflows through a user-friendly, drag-and-drop interface. This tool integrates various data sources, applies spatial and non-spatial analyses, and generates dynamic visualizations without extensive coding. By automating repetitive tasks and facilitating collaboration, CARTO Workflows enhances efficiency and supports informed decision-making. For more information, please refer to the Annex Annex 3 CARTO Workflows.

We have developed new components for CARTO Workflows, incorporating advanced functionalities from the EMERALDS project and other technologies. These components seamlessly integrate with CARTO Workflows, allowing users to utilize EMERALDS mobility data types and analysis capabilities. This enhancement boosts the analytical power and versatility of CARTO Workflows, enabling sophisticated geospatial analyses and visualization of complex mobility patterns, thereby improving workflow efficiency and expanding application possibilities.

As part of this deliverable, CARTO has integrated a new set of components into Workflows, enabling users to access UDFs and procedures directly from a visual interface.

- **Call Procedure^{xviii}**: This component executes an arbitrary CALL SQL statement.
- **Custom SQL Select^{xix}**: This component executes an arbitrary SELECT SQL statement.
- **Import from URL^{xx}**: This component writes an input table to a non-temporary location.
- **Spatial match^{xxi}**: This component writes an input table to a non-temporary location.
- **ST Delaunay Voronoi^{xxii}**: This component computes a Delaunay triangulation based on an input table with points.
- **ST Voronoi^{xxiii}**: This component computes a Voronoi tessellation based on an input table with points.
- **Create isolines^{xxiv}**: This component computes isolines.
- **Create routes^{xxv}**: This component creates routes between origin and destination points stored in a table.
- **H3 Polyfill^{xxvi}**: This generates a table with indices of all H3 cells included within a given extent for a given resolution.
- **Quadbin Polyfill^{xxvii}**: This generates a table with indices of all Quadbin cells included within a given extent for a given resolution.
- **Distance matrix^{xxviii}**: This component creates a new table with a distance matrix computed for the geometries contained in an input table.

^{xviii} <https://docs.carto.com/carto-user-manual/workflows/components/custom#call-procedure>

^{xix} <https://docs.carto.com/carto-user-manual/workflows/components/custom#custom-sql-select>

^{xx} <https://docs.carto.com/carto-user-manual/workflows/components/input-output>

^{xxi} <https://docs.carto.com/carto-user-manual/workflows/components/joins#spatial-match>

^{xxii} <https://docs.carto.com/carto-user-manual/workflows/components/spatial-analysis#st-delaunay-polygons>

^{xxiii} <https://docs.carto.com/carto-user-manual/workflows/components/spatial-analysis#st-voronoi>

^{xxiv} https://docs.carto.com/carto-user-manual/workflows/components/spatial-constructors#create_isolines

^{xxv} https://docs.carto.com/carto-user-manual/workflows/components/spatial-constructors#create_routes

^{xxvi} <https://docs.carto.com/carto-user-manual/workflows/components/spatial-indexes#h3-polyfill>

^{xxvii} <https://docs.carto.com/carto-user-manual/workflows/components/spatial-indexes#quadbin-polyfill>

^{xxviii} <https://docs.carto.com/carto-user-manual/workflows/components/spatial-operations#distance-matrix>

- **Distance to nearest^{xxix}**: This component creates a new table with a distance matrix computed for the geometries contained in an input table.
- **Trade areas^{xxx}**: This component creates regions around specific point objects in the input table.

2.3 Integration of AI/ML emeralds

Some of the most advanced capabilities of EMERALDS services involve the use of Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Machine Learning (ML). These features enable sophisticated data analyses and predictive insights, but their integration can be complex due to varying requirements across different data warehouses.

Table 5 summarizes the deployment and integration of WP4 emeralds in CARTO, detailing the catalogue, deployment/integration methods, and repository links for each service developed per task.

Table 5 Deployment and integration of WP4 emeralds in CARTO per Task

EMERALDS Catalogue	D/I	Means of Deployment/ Integration	Repository Link
Extreme Scale MDA at the CC (T4.1)			
Dropoff / Destination Prediction	Yes	Working connection from CARTO to a PostgreSQL instance in MAIaaS platform or other envs.	Project's Github
Monitoring and Forecasting Shared Mobility Demand	Yes	Pending connection from CARTO to a PostgreSQL instance in MAIaaS platform or other envs.	Under Construction
Probabilistic Trip Chaining	Yes	Working connection from CARTO to a PostgreSQL instance in MAIaaS platform or other envs.	Project's Github
Trajectory Data Analysis	Yes	Working connection from CARTO import PyMEOS (as a python library in Snowflake)	Project's Github
Real-time Extreme Scale Map Matching (SiStema)	Planned (API pending)	CARTO to provide an external function according to the API exposed by SiStema.	Project's Github
Active & Federated Learning over Mobility Data (T4.2)			
Traffic State / Flow Forecasting (UPRC)	No	Data ingestion of results generated in external executions feasible	Project's Github
Parking Occupancy Garage Prediction (AIT)	No		Project's Github
Crowd Density Prediction (AIT, INLE, TUD)	No		Project's Github
Active Learning & XAI for Crowd Prediction (AIT)	No		Project's Github
Active Learning for Risk Category Classification (AIT)	No		Under Construction

^{xxix} <https://docs.carto.com/carto-user-manual/workflows/components/spatial-operations#distance-to-nearest>

^{xxx} https://docs.carto.com/carto-user-manual/workflows/components/spatial-operations#trade_areas

Federated Learning for Mobility Data (AIT)	No		Under Construction
Mobility AI-as-a-Service (T4.3)			
Data Management (ATOS)	Yes	Data Warehouses interconnected. Inference results generated on MAIaaS are pulled to CARTO Data Warehouses.	Project's Github
ML Model Development Framework (ATOS)	Yes		Project's Github
ML Model Deployment Framework (ATOS)	Yes		Project's Github
Federated Learning Module (ATOS)	Yes		Project's Github

The EMERALDS-CARTO integration mapping for WP4 focuses on **Extreme Scale MDA at the CC (T4.1)** as can be seen in the table above. For Dropoff/Destination Prediction (UPRC), Monitoring and Forecasting Shared Mobility Demand (UPRC), Probabilistic Trip Chaining (INLE), and Trajectory Data Analysis (AIT), there is integration with CARTO through connections to the Postgres in the MAIaaS platform or importing PyMEOs⁹ (as a Python library in Snowflake). Real-time Extreme Scale Map Matching (Sistema) might be integrated by M36, as SISTEMA will expose an API, allowing CARTO to have external functions according to that API.

For **Active & Federated Learning over Mobility Data (T4.2)**, Traffic State/Flow Forecasting (UPRC), Parking Garage Occupancy Prediction (AIT), Crowd Density Prediction (AIT, INLE, TUD), Active Learning & XAI for Crowd Prediction (AIT), Active Learning for Risk Category Classification (AIT), and Federated Learning for Mobility Data (AIT) are not directly integrated or deployed with CARTO due to their predictive and dynamic characteristics. At this stage of maturity, the services are interesting in feeding their results for visualization in CARTO through data exchanges with their execution environments, for instance the MAIaaS platform.

Mobility AI-as-a-Service (T4.3) includes Data Management (ATOS), ML Model Development Framework (ATOS), and Federated Learning Module (ATOS), all of which are integrated with CARTO through connections to the Postgres in the ATOS platform.

2.3.1 Integration and Connection with the Trajectory Data Analysis emerald

Over the course of the first 18 months of the project, we have successfully integrated the Moving Pandas library^{xxxix}, a key component of the EMERALDS services developed within Work Package 4 (WP4). These services offer advanced tools for trajectory data analysis and visualization, enhancing our ability to process and analyze movement data with high precision. For more detailed deep dive, please go to Annex 1 and inspect an example of integration with Moving Pandas. In addition, it has also been added to the GitHub repo, see footnote ^{xxxix}.

This integration required addressing several technical challenges to ensure seamless functionality across diverse data environments. The emeralds developed on top of Moving Pandas, yield

^{xxxix} <https://movingpandas.org/>

^{xxxix} <https://github.com/emeralds-horizon/Cartoblog?tab=readme-ov-file>

significantly enhanced analytics services, enabling detailed tracking and analysis of movement patterns. This improvement enriches the user experience and lays a robust foundation for further AI and ML applications within the CARTO platform. Moving forward, we aim to continue integrating more advanced AI and ML tools, expanding the capabilities of the EMERALDS ecosystem for comprehensive data analysis and informed decision-making.

The trajectory data analysis capabilities of EMERALDS are designed with callouts and dependencies to the Moving Pandas library. Its integration has been achieved by implementing User Defined Functions (UDFs) in Python within a Snowflake environment, which supports Python UDFs. This setup allows us to create functions that invoke MovingPandas^{xxxiii} functionalities. Specifically, three UDF functions were created in Snowflake:

- **OutlierCleaner:** A speed-based outlier cleaner that removes spikes in the trajectory when the speed exceeds the provided threshold value.
- **TrajectoryClip:** Return trajectory segments clipped by the given polygon.
- **TemporalSplitter:** Split trajectories into sub-trajectories using regular time intervals.

Similarly to MovingPandas, the PyMEOS^{xxxiv} library can also be integrated with the CARTO platform within a Snowflake environment using Python UDFs. PyMEOS, which has recently become available in the conda-forge channel, offers advanced capabilities for temporal and spatiotemporal data management and analysis. This integration allows us to leverage PyMEOS's powerful features to enhance data analytics workflows whilst unlocking support for novel workflows, providing users with more sophisticated tools for handling complex spatio-temporal/trajectory data.

For the next stages of the project, we plan to explore this integration further. Our goal is to create additional UDFs that utilize PyMEOS functionalities as part of the Analytics Toolbox, thereby expanding the analytical capabilities of the EMERALDS services. This effort will involve rigorous testing and development to ensure seamless functionality and robust performance.

2.3.1.1 Visualization on CARTO Dashboards

Using the aforementioned EMERALDS component and running the analysis, the results are illustrated in the dashboard below (Figure 2-5). The output of the hotspot analysis was:

- The P value is the significance value which may allow us to reject the null hypothesis of our analysis. So, if the null hypothesis was "there is no spatio-temporal clustering of collisions" then where cells fall under a set threshold, we can reject this. Typically, that threshold will be 0.01 or 0.05, associated with a confidence level of 99% or 95% respectively.
- The GI* value indicates the strength of clustering. Positive values indicate a strong spatial clustering of positive values relative to the wider dataset, while negative values indicate the reverse.

In the dashboards below, the *average index (GI*)* across time for each H3 cell is illustrated, having only statistically significant clusters of high values in magnitude. This visualization incorporates SQL

^{xxxiii} <https://movingpandas.org/>

^{xxxiv} <https://pypi.org/project/pymeos/>

Parameters to make the dashboards more user-friendly and interactive. These allow the user to add placeholders into your SQL (see below: **{{time_from}}** and **{{time_to}}**) to allow end users to interact with the data in a controlled way. Here, they are able to view the average GI* value over a specific time period - perhaps rush hour or late at night. The users can filter by specific dates and hours and compare the results visually to get more insights into how the patterns change over space and time.

Figure 2-5: Dashboard showing the results of the analysis for Taxi Hotpost in the city of Porto using the Emerald component MovingPandas integrated with CARTO.

Map can be accessed here. ^{xxxv}

^{xxxv} <https://clausa.app.carto.com/map/b5047019-e4f7-4242-b90a-8cad863a7f39>

3 Security and Data Governance Layer

In the context of Task 2.3 entitled “Security and Data Governance”, TUC implements and delivers a set of tools to ensure the security and trustworthiness of the project’s edge devices and transmitted data across the different layers of the EMERALDS architecture. As it has been noted in the deliverable D2.1 “EMERALDS Reference Architecture”, the security layer consists of three independent tools and services.

The security tools developed in Task 2.3 are the following:

- **Security tool #1:** RATEE is a remote attestation service under a Trusted Execution Environment. RATEE is a secure environment built to ensure the trustworthiness and confidentiality between edge nodes operating within the EMERALDS architecture.
- **Security tool #2:** Secure communication channels for the protection (encryption/decryption) of the data exchanged between the devices and services of EMERALDS. This component uses a state-of-the-art peer-to-peer Virtual Private Network (VPN), called “n2n” VPN, and it is customized and configured according to the devices’ requirements that operate within the EMERALDS architecture.
- **Security tool #3:** An FPGA-based Network Intrusion Detection System (NIDS) that enables fast network packet inspection for prompt threat identification and alerting.

Table 6 provides a comprehensive overview of how EMERALDS Security and Data Governance Layer components developed under T2.3 are integrated into the CARTO platform environment.

Table 6 Deployment and integration of T2.3 Security and Data Governance emeralds

EMERALDS Catalogue	D/I	Means of Deployment/Integration	Repository Link
Secure Communication Channels	No	The operational nature of this emerald does not require visualization through the CARTO platform.	NA
FPGA-based Network Intrusion Detection System	Maybe (M36)	This emerald is currently under development, and it will be possibly integrated with the CARTO platform in the following months.	
Remote Attestation in Trusted Execution Environments	Yes	The CARTO platform visualizes alerts, which originate from devices' integrity checks. The devices' locations are shown in the map.	Section 4.1

The EMERALDS-CARTO mapping integration for TUC focuses on **Security and Data Governance (T2.3)**. For Secure Communication Channels (TUC), there is no integration with CARTO because the operational nature of this emerald does not require visualization through the CARTO platform.

The FPGA-based Network Intrusion Detection System (TUC) is planned for integration after the submission of D2.6 on M24 as it is currently under development.

Remote Attestation in Trusted Execution Environments (TUC) is already integrated with CARTO. This integration allows the CARTO platform to visualize alerts originating from devices' integrity checks, with the devices' locations shown on the map, enhancing the utility of CARTO for users.

3.1 Demonstration of integrated RATEE service in CARTO

As presented in Table 6, the security tool that is currently integrated with the CARTO platform is the security tool #1, namely “RATEE”. The security tool #2, also referred to as “Secure Communication Channels” will not be integrated with the CARTO platform, since the nature of its operation does not require visualization. Finally, the output of the security tool #3 “FPGA-based NIDS” is expected to be visualized through the CARTO platform in the next version of this deliverable D2.5 (“*Demonstration of integrated services (EMERALDS) v2*”), since it is currently under development.

In this section, the alerts visualization as generated from the RATEE tool is presented. As stated in D2.1, the RATEE tool deploys a “Listener” in a target node, which an “Attester” can send attestation requests to. The target node executes sensitive calculations (encryption/decryption and secure key loading) in a secure environment named Trusted Execution Environment. The attester can send parallel requests to multiple nodes, and the responses it receives can be visualized.

Figure 3-1 presents the current experimental setup in a lab environment. In the setup presented, the “Secure Communication Channels” tool is included, to ensure the security and privacy of the data transmission. The different devices in Figure 2-1Figure 3-1 (i.e., “Device 1” with IP address 10.9.9.1, “Device 2” with IP address 10.9.9.3, and “Desktop” with IP address 10.9.9.2) correspond to different edge devices of the EMERALDS devices ecosystem. Currently, the EMERALDS Use Cases are not equipped with edge devices. Thus, the RATEE tool can be only demonstrated in a laboratory environment, simulating a realistic use case scenario. When edge devices that meet the hardware requirements of the RATEE tool become available, the tool will be deployed and tested in a real use case scenario in the context of EMERALDS.

Figure 3-1: The current RATEE setup for experimentation and demonstration in a lab environment. The devices used are two edge devices and one desktop machine.

As the CARTO visualization platform displays entries as geospatial data, we simulate the locations of the three devices in our laboratory environment as we would expect to be presented in a real usage scenario of the EMERALDS. Each alert that is generated is written into a table (e.g., “.csv” file), which is then imported manually to the CARTO Platform. In this deliverable’s later version (D2.5), this process is expected to be automated by utilizing a local database to store each device’s state.

In the demonstration that was conducted with its output being presented in Figure 3-2, it is shown that all devices can be trusted, after performing an integrity check to each device using the RATEE tool. In Figure 3-2, we can see that all three devices are marked with a green dot, which indicates that the devices are checked by the attester and that they can be trusted. In the map, the entries with the state and the IP addresses of the devices are visualized. In Figure 3-3, the case that a device fails to pass the attestation check is presented (i.e., device with IP address 10.9.9.1). When a device can not be attested, the corresponding entry in the map is marked with a red dot, while in the table it is marked as “untrusted”. Finally, for a detailed alert presentation, a table widget can be created to show the alert resulting from a specific tuple with the following information: {IP address, port, timestamp and geospatial location of the device}.

Figure 3-2: CARTO visualization page showing the current trust state of 3 devices with a table widget for additional information.

Figure 3-3: CARTO visualization page showing the trust state of 3 devices after 10 seconds of activity, indicating that one device became untrustworthy.

4 Analysis of Map Vector Tile format

In the EMERALDS, ULB and CARTO aim to enhance the Mapbox Vector Tiles standard by incorporating native support for spatiotemporal data. This initiative is structured into three main levels of development: (i) defining the data transfer format, (ii) implementing the standard format in MobilityDB and CARTO, and (iii) creating an initial client implementation for visualization using deck.gl. The progress of this effort is expected to significantly benefit EMERALDS by providing enhanced capabilities for handling and visualizing spatiotemporal data across various applications and use cases. Beyond the technical benefits of assessing the MVT format, this work enhances data interoperability but also lays the foundation for seamless integration and analysis of complex spatiotemporal datasets as well as streamlines the exchange of trajectory and mobility data across different platforms and systems, promoting consistency and reliability in data sharing practices. Furthermore, these efforts are aligned with EMERALDS WP6 standardization activities triggering not only specific technical developments within EMERALDS but also fosters collaboration with industry partners and stakeholders who rely on standardized data formats.

The Map Vector Tile Format was originally created by a company called **Mapbox** as the *Mapbox Vector Tile format* (MVT)^{xxxvi} more than 10 years ago. This format was designed to efficiently deliver geographic data for rendering maps on the web and mobile devices. The use of *vector tiles* allows for more flexible, scalable, and interactive maps compared to traditional raster tiles¹⁰. Since its introduction, the format has been widely adopted and has become a standard for delivering vector-based map data.

In this deliverable, we are working on next-generation technologies to improve its performance to handle different geospatial data types such as mobility or raster. Therefore we are looking at the format itself, (section 4.1), the underlying GPU technologies for visualization, (section 4.2) and the GeoParquet standard (section 4.3).

4.1 Comparison of MVT with deck.gl native format

We started this task by looking at the main issues that MVT format has in consideration for Mobility Data.

Handling mobility data with the MVT format presents several significant challenges. The high volume and complexity of mobility data, which includes constant movement tracking and various attributes such as speed and direction, demand robust data processing capabilities. Ensuring real-time data processing with low latency and maintaining synchronization across tiles is critical for applications that rely on up-to-date information, as in the case of distribute IoT devices and monitoring of transport infrastructures. Additionally, achieving high precision and accuracy while managing and representing detailed data can be complex, and any errors or inaccuracies must be effectively handled.

Performance optimization is another key challenge, as rendering large datasets quickly, especially on mobile devices with limited resources, requires efficient data compression techniques. Scalability and

^{xxxvi} <https://docs.mapbox.com/data/tilesets/guides/vector-tiles-introduction/>

load balancing are essential for managing large volumes of data and handling peak loads. Privacy and security concerns must be addressed to protect individual privacy and ensure secure data transmission. Finally, integrating data from various sources, complying with standards, and effectively representing temporal dynamics are crucial for creating a reliable and user-friendly mobility data visualization system using the MVT format¹¹.

We are actively working on comparing the MVT format with the native deck.gl format as a potential solution to some of these issues.

Deck.gl's native binary format is tailored for high-performance visualization, leveraging GPU acceleration for rendering large and complex datasets. It is particularly suited for applications requiring real-time updates and interactivity. However, it is less widely adopted and requires specific preprocessing of data, making it more specialized for use within Deck.gl's ecosystem.

We still continue doing research on technologies such as Apache Arrow to overcome some of the limitations and increase standardization.

4.2 WebGPU integration with deck.gl

As part of our EMERALDS delivery related to the analysis of the Map Vector Tile format, one of the most significant advancements we implemented was the transition from WebGL to WebGPU in deck.gl 9.0^{xxxvii}. (Figure 4-1). Previously, deck.gl utilized WebGL, a widely-used web standard for rendering 2D and 3D graphics within compatible web browsers without the need for plugins¹². While WebGL offered robust performance and broad compatibility, enabling deck.gl to render complex visualizations effectively, its capabilities were limited compared to the more modern WebGPU.

WebGPU, developed as a successor to WebGL, offers improved performance, more direct access to GPU hardware, and better support for parallel computing tasks¹³. This transition allows deck.gl to leverage these enhancements, resulting in smoother, more efficient rendering of complex visualizations and datasets. By adopting WebGPU, deck.gl 9.0 not only future-proofs its framework for the evolving landscape of web graphics but also significantly boosts the performance and scalability of applications built on the platform. This change marks a major step forward in delivering high-quality, interactive geospatial visualizations with unprecedented speed and efficiency, enhancing our ability to analyze and visualize Map Vector Tile formats as part of the EMERALD project.

Figure 4-1: deck.gl v9 banner announcement in CARTO

Additionally, deck.gl v9 now supports TypeScript, enhancing code reliability and development efficiency. TypeScript's static typing helps catch errors early, reducing bugs and speeding up

^{xxxvii} <https://deck.gl/>

development. Features like enhanced autocompletion and IntelliSense make coding more intuitive. Static typing also promotes clearer coding practices, easing maintenance and scalability. Aligning with the trend towards statically typed languages in the JavaScript ecosystem, this update makes deck.gl more robust and developer-friendly.

The release notes for deck.gl 9.0 are available on its github repo^{xxxviii} and^{xxxix}.The official announcement of this can be found on the following link in the footnote.^{xl}

4.3 Development of GeoParquet

The datasets exchanged by geospatial software products have to be structured in a way that products by other vendors can read the data and interpret the information they contain. The encoding of geospatial data (typically utilized in mobility analytics operations and integral part of studying and understanding mobility patterns) has been a recurring challenge towards performant visualization, spatial analytics and faster ETL approaches.

To facilitate the exchange of messages and data containing geospatial information, the OGC has established a set of data models and encoding standards. These standards define the guidelines for structuring and organizing geospatial data for specific applications. Some standards outline conceptual models, while others provide logical models meant to be implemented using various encoding formats. Additionally, many of these standards include instructions on how to encode information according to the logical models and in specific formats.

Geoparquet^{xli} is a standard developed by CARTO and other partners for storing vector geospatial data in the Parquet file format. This initiative aligns geospatial data storage practices with modern data engineering standards, facilitating seamless integration with data warehouses like Google BigQuery and Snowflake. By using Parquet, Geoparquet ensures high performance and efficient data storage, breaking down data silos and allowing geospatial data to be managed alongside other types of big data. This standardization supports the convergence of geospatial data with the broader data ecosystem, enhancing interoperability, scalability, and future-proofing of geospatial data lakes

GeoParquet provides a novel approach in storing geospatial vector data (points, lines, polygons) in Apache Parquet, a renown columnar storage format tailored for tabular data (Figure 4-2). Leveraging on the wide ecosystem of tools and support of the latter, GeoParquet comprises a reliable storage solution for geometries. Because GeoParquet is not a separate format, any program that can read Parquet is able to load GeoParquet as well, even if it can't make sense of the geometry information.

The two main things that GeoParquet defines on top of Parquet are how to encode geometries in the geometry column and how to include metadata like the geometries' Coordinate Reference System (CRS).

^{xxxviii} <https://deck.gl/docs/whats-new#deckgl-v90>

^{xxxix} <https://deck.gl/docs>

^{xl} <https://carto.com/blog/announcing-deck-gl-v9-webgpu-ready-with-typescript-support>

^{xli} <https://geoparquet.org/>

Because GeoParquet stores geometries in standard Well-Known Binary (WKB), it supports any vector geometry type defined in the OGC Simple Features specification. This includes the standard building blocks of Point, LineString, Polygon, MultiPoint, MultiLineString, MultiPolygon, and GeometryCollection. A best practice is to store only geometries with the same type, as that allows readers to know which geometry type is stored without scanning the entire file¹⁴.

Figure 4-2: GeoParquet file diagram layout

In addition, CARTO is working on a standardization initiative aiming to store raster data in the Parquet file format, extending the Geoparquet standard used for vector data to rasters. Currently utilized in Google BigQuery and Snowflake, this format is designed to break down data silos, align geospatial data practices with broader data world standards, and enhance performance and future-proofing. This initiative supports the integration of geospatial data with other data types, ensuring that the benefits of big data technologies are fully realized for geospatial applications.

In the domain of Earth Observation data, RasterFrames^{xliii} has developed a DataFrame centric framework that supports spatiotemporal queries, map algebra raster operations and compatibility with Apache Spark ML algorithms. Thereon computing continuum solutions can be implemented since the solution can be easily scaled to run on cluster and cloud compute resources, enabling a bottom-up analysis with satellite imagery.

For mobility analytics, raster data is particularly useful for analyzing environmental factors that influence transportation systems, such as elevation changes that affect vehicle routes or temperature variations that impact road conditions. By incorporating raster data into mobility analyses, users can gain a more comprehensive understanding of how various factors interact to influence movement patterns and transportation efficiency.

^{xliii} <https://rasterframes.io/description.html>

5 Conclusions and next steps

D2.4 summarises the technical work related to the first deployment of the most mature EMERALDS services based on D3.1 and D4.1 results, in alignment with the EMERALDS reference architecture in D2.1, creating dashboards leveraging the advanced geospatial data visualisation suite in the CARTO platform and the CARTO Builder component that are integral parts of the data pipeline demonstrations envisioned in each EMERALDS Use Case (D5.2-D5.7), integration of advanced analytics capabilities in response to the elevated requirements and complexity of the operations served by emeralds, the security hardening of the data workflows and the potential of innovative data formats and standards in improving the performance of web-native visualizations enabling real-time dashboards.

Integration within the CARTO Analytics Toolbox has been pivotal. The introduction of the new Routing Service (2.1.1) paves the ground for emeralds to reach their capabilities and performance in the CARTO environment. Furthermore, the integration with emeralds build on top of MobilityDB (2.1.2) enhances spatial data management, facilitating complex geospatial analyses.

The release of new components in CARTO Workflows, streamlines workflows, allowing users to create, manage, and share geospatial analyses seamlessly generated with emeralds. The integration and connection with the Trajectory Data Analysis EMERALD (2.3.1) exemplifies EMERALDS' approach to leveraging AI/ML for enhanced mobility analytics, empowering users to derive deeper insights from trajectory data.

The analysis of Map Vector Tile (MVT) format (4.1) and its comparison with deck.gl native format (4.2) demonstrates EMERALDS' commitment to advancing data visualization capabilities. The development of GeoParquet (4.3) further enhances data storage efficiency and accessibility, supporting scalable and high-performance data analytics. Furthermore, the promotion of innovative standards and open technologies facilitating the design of extreme scale applications in the cloud for urban mobility data is tied with the EMERALDS objective to create an open innovation ecosystem that fosters data interoperability and simplified interconnections between domain specific and agnostic software solutions.

For the next version of the deliverable, in M36, we plan to have the rest of the core developed in order to further refine the integrations with the emeralds and create more demos as well as increase the overall usability. Having seen all of the above, it remains to comment that there is still some way to go in terms of the synchronization of the different EMERALDS in the CARTO systems, however, with the above connections and evidence, the foundations for the effective deployment of the services have been set.

Concerning CARTO developments, it has been demonstrated that EMERALDS has made a great push in terms of further optimization and new capabilities of the map visualization systems presented in CARTO. In conclusion, the EMERALDS project has successfully integrated advanced geospatial analytics, AI/ML capabilities, and innovative data formats into the CARTO platform. These advancements not only enhance the platform's analytical capacity but also pave the way for future

innovations in urban mobility data analytics. Moving forward, continued collaboration and refinement of these integrated solutions will be crucial for the next Development, Implementation, Integration and Assessment Cycles, leading to mature results, identifying key learning for the adoption of the EMERALDS technology meanwhile maximizing EMERALDS impact.

ANNEXES

Annex 1 Moving Pandas integration example

OutlierCleaner

- Speed-based outlier cleaner that cuts away spikes in the trajectory when the speed exceeds the provided speed threshold value

Figure 0-1 depicts an instance of the code for the Outlier Cleaner routine:

```
CREATE OR REPLACE FUNCTION CARTO_DATABASE.CARTO.OutlierCleaner(geom ARRAY, t ARRAY,
vmax FLOAT)
RETURNS ARRAY
LANGUAGE PYTHON
RUNTIME_VERSION = 3.11
PACKAGES = ('numpy', 'pandas', 'geopandas', 'movingpandas', 'shapely')
HANDLER = 'udf'
AS $$
import numpy as np
import pandas as pd
import geopandas as gpd
import movingpandas as mpd
import shapely
from shapely.geometry import shape, mapping, Point
from shapely.validation import make_valid
from datetime import datetime, timedelta

def udf(geom, t, vmax):
    valid_df = pd.DataFrame(geom, columns=['geometry'])
    valid_df['t'] = pd.to_datetime(t)
    valid_df['geometry'] = valid_df['geometry'].apply(lambda x:shapely.wkt.loads(x))
    gdf = gpd.GeoDataFrame(valid_df, geometry='geometry', crs='epsg:4326')
    gdf = gdf.set_index('t')
    traj = mpd.Trajectory(gdf, 1)
    traj.add_speed(units=('km', 'h'))
    traj_sm = mpd.OutlierCleaner(traj).clean(v_max=vmax, units=("km", "h"))
    if traj_sm.is_valid():
        traj_sm.add_speed(overwrite=True, units=('km', 'h'))
    else:
        return []
    res = traj_sm.to_point_gdf()
    res['geometry'] = res['geometry'].apply(lambda x: shapely.wkt.dumps(x))
    return res.reset_index().drop('traj_id', axis=1).values
$$;
```

Figure 0-1: Outlier Cleaner snippet

TrajectoryClip

- Return trajectory segments clipped by the given polygon.

Figure 0-2 shows a code snippet from theTrajectoryClip subcomponent:

```
CREATE OR REPLACE FUNCTION CARTO_DATABASE.CARTO.trajectory_clip(geom ARRAY, t ARRAY,
polygon GEOGRAPHY)
RETURNS ARRAY
LANGUAGE PYTHON
RUNTIME_VERSION = 3.11
PACKAGES = ('numpy', 'pandas', 'geopandas', 'movingpandas', 'shapely')
HANDLER = 'udf'
AS $$
import numpy as np
import pandas as pd
import geopandas as gpd
import movingpandas as mpd
import shapely
from shapely.geometry import shape, mapping, Point, Polygon
from shapely.validation import make_valid
from datetime import datetime, timedelta

def udf(geom, t, polygon):
    valid_df = pd.DataFrame(geom, columns=['geometry'])
    valid_df['t'] = pd.to_datetime(t)
    valid_df['geometry'] = valid_df['geometry'].apply(lambda x:shapely.wkt.loads(x))
    gdf = gpd.GeoDataFrame(valid_df, geometry='geometry', crs='epsg:4326')
    gdf = gdf.set_index('t')
    traj = mpd.Trajectory(gdf, 1)
    traj_sm = traj.clip(shape(polygon))
    if len(traj_sm.trajectories)>0:
        res = traj_sm.to_point_gdf()
        res['geometry'] = res['geometry'].apply(lambda x: shapely.wkt.dumps(x))
        return res.reset_index().values
    else:
        return []
$$;
```

Figure 0-2: Trajectory Clipping snippet

TemporalSplitter

- Split trajectories into sub-trajectories using regular time intervals.

Figure 0-3 illustrates the code for the Temporal Splitter:

```
CREATE OR REPLACE FUNCTION CARTO_DATABASE.CARTO.TemporalSplitter(geom ARRAY, t ARRAY,
mode STRING)
RETURNS ARRAY
LANGUAGE PYTHON
RUNTIME_VERSION = 3.11
PACKAGES = ('numpy', 'pandas', 'geopandas', 'movingpandas', 'shapely')
HANDLER = 'udf'
AS $$
import numpy as np
```

```
import pandas as pd
import geopandas as gpd
import movingpandas as mpd
import shapely
from shapely.geometry import shape, mapping, Point, Polygon
from shapely.validation import make_valid
from datetime import datetime, timedelta

def udf(geom, t, mode):
    valid_df = pd.DataFrame(geom, columns=['geometry'])
    valid_df['t'] = pd.to_datetime(t)
    valid_df['geometry'] = valid_df['geometry'].apply(lambda x:shapely.wkt.loads(x))
    gdf = gpd.GeoDataFrame(valid_df, geometry='geometry', crs='epsg:4326')
    gdf = gdf.set_index('t')
    traj = mpd.Trajectory(gdf, 1)
    traj_sm = mpd.TemporalSplitter(traj).split(mode=mode)
    if len(traj_sm.trajectories)>0:
        res = traj_sm.to_point_gdf()
        res['geometry'] = res['geometry'].apply(lambda x: shapely.wkt.dumps(x))
        return res.reset_index().values
    else:
        return []

$$;
```

Figure 0-3: Temporal Splitter Code snippet

Similarly, as with MovingPandas, it is possible to integrate PyMEOS library with CARTO in Snowflake environment using UDFs in Python. PyMEOS became available in the conda-forge channel recently.

Annex 2 CARTO Platform

CARTO^{xliii} is a Location Intelligence platform for modern data stack. It enables organizations to use spatial data and analysis for more efficient delivery routes, better behavioral marketing, strategic store placements, and much more.

CARTO is a cloud-first spatial platform built for accelerated, modern GIS. It runs natively on top of the cloud data warehouse platform (e.g. Google BigQuery, Snowflake, AWS Redshift, etc.), providing easy access to highly scalable spatial analysis and visualization capabilities in the cloud, whether for analytics, app development, and data engineering. CARTO is available in both cloud and self-hosted deployments.

Figure 0-4: CARTO platform overview

CARTO platform (Figure 0-4) highlights the comprehensive capabilities of the CARTO platform for spatial data analysis and visualization. At its core, CARTO provides tools and APIs that enable the analysis, visualization, exploration, reporting, and development of spatial data solutions. Key features include automated workflows, a Data Observatory offering diverse datasets such as financial and demographic data, and an Analytics Toolbox with tools for clustering and statistics. CARTO integrates seamlessly with major cloud data warehouses like Google BigQuery, Snowflake, and Amazon Redshift, enhancing scalability and data processing efficiency. The platform supports deployment on leading cloud platforms including Google Cloud, AWS, and Microsoft Azure. For developers, CARTO offers frameworks like CARTO for React and deck.gl, allowing the creation of custom spatial data applications. The Builder tool facilitates the creation of interactive maps and visualizations. Overall, CARTO’s cloud-first approach ensures high scalability and accessibility, making it a powerful solution for modern spatial data analysis needs.

^{xliii} <https://docs.carto.com/getting-started/cartoin-a-nutshell>

Annex 3 CARTO Workflows

CARTO focused on the creation and refinement of workflows to transform them into a visual language. This shift towards a visual approach allows users to build, manage, and execute complex workflows with greater ease and understanding. The primary objective was to develop a system that supports drag-and-drop functionality, where users can visually connect different components to form comprehensive workflows. Figure 0-5 shows a Workflow example.

Figure 0-5 Workflow diagram with Snowflake connection

In the following video^{xliv}, CARTO Workflows is introduced as a powerful feature designed to simplify spatial analytics for users of all skill levels. The key points covered include:

- **Intuitive Interface:** CARTO Workflows offers a cloud-native interface that is easy to use. It allows users to build complex spatial analyses using a visual drag-and-drop approach.
- **User Accessibility:** The tool is accessible to data scientists, analysts, and developers, making it easy for anyone to integrate spatial data into their projects.
- **Seamless Cloud Integration:** CARTO Workflows integrates seamlessly with big data warehouses such as Google BigQuery and Snowflake. This integration enhances the spatial analytics capabilities by leveraging the power of these platforms.

This tutorial video^{xlv} provides a concise, step-by-step guide on how to get started with CARTO Workflows:

- **Initial Setup:** Demonstrates the process of creating a new workflow and adding data sources.

^{xliv} <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=oeN1PssPfCc>

^{xlv} <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=YQD9W8ur0ZU>

- **Analysis Tools:** Shows how to use various analysis tools within CARTO Workflows.
- **Ease of Use:** Highlights the drag-and-drop interface, making it easy to build and execute spatial analyses quickly.
- **Integration:** Emphasizes integration with cloud data warehouses for enhanced data management.
- **Collaboration:** Showcases real-time collaboration capabilities, allowing multiple users to work together seamlessly.

This last video^{xlvi} demonstrates the utilization of the CARTO Workflows Gallery for conducting no-code spatial analysis. The demonstration illustrates the process of leveraging pre-built templates from the gallery, which can be easily dragged and dropped into the user's workspace. This feature significantly simplifies the workflow creation process, eliminating the need to build analytical workflows from scratch and thereby enhancing efficiency and user experience.

^{xlvi} <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=6nsA0egzx74>

Annex 4: Ethics Checklist and Questionnaire

Ethics Checklist and Questionnaire

THIS FORM NEEDS TO BE FILLED-IN BY THE DELIVERABLE LEADER BEFORE, DURING AND AFTER THE WORK LEADING TO THE RELEVANT DELIVERABLE. DELIVERABLE LEADERS ARE ENCOURAGED TO DISCUSS EACH ACTIVE QUESTIONNAIRE WITH THE ETHICS COMMITTEE. EACH OPEN QUESTIONNAIRE SHOULD EITHER BE STORED IN THE PROJECT MS TEAMS DIRECTORY OR A LINK MADE AVAILABLE TO THE RELEVANT SHARED DOC. COMPLETED FORMS NEED TO BE SUBMITTED AS PART OF THE DELIVERABLE Q/A PROCESS. IN THE EVENT OF COMMENTS AND/OR QUESTIONS BY THE ETHICS COMMITTEE, THE DELIVERABLE LEADER HAS TO PROVIDE RELEVANT RESPONSES AND/OR CLARIFICATIONS IN A TIMELY MANNER

A. PERSONAL DATA

1. Has **personal data** going to be processed for the completion of this deliverable?

NO

- If “yes”, do they refer only to individuals connected to project partners or to third parties as well?

2. Are “**special categories of personal data**” going to be processed for this deliverable? (whereby these include personal data revealing racial or ethnic origin, political opinions, religious or philosophical beliefs, and trade union membership, as well as, genetic data, biometric data, data concerning health or data concerning a natural person's sex life or sexual orientation)

NO

3. Has the **consent** of the individuals concerned been acquired prior to the processing of their personal data?

N/A

- If “yes”, is it based on the Project’s Informed Consent Form, either on the provided Template or on other attached herein Template?
- If “no” is it based on a different legal basis?

4. In the event of processing of personal data, is the processing:

N/A

- obviously “**Fair and lawful**”, meaning executed in a fair manner and following consent of the individuals concerned or based on another - acknowledged as adequate and proportionate as per above - legal basis?
- Performed for a **specific (project-related) cause** only?

- Executed on the basis of the principle of **proportionality and data minimisation** (meaning that only data that are **necessary** for the processing purposes are being processed and such deductive reasoning is documented)?
 - Based on **high-quality, updated and precise personal data**?
5. Are there any provisions for a storage limitation period of the personal data-in case of storage- after which they must be erased?

N/A

6. Are all **other lawful requirements** for the processing of the data (for example, **notification of the competent Data Protection Authority(s)** or undergoing a **DPIA procedure** and consulting with the competent DPA, if and where applicable) adhered to and on what legislative basis are such notifications justified as necessary or dismissed as unnecessary?

N/A

7. Have individuals been **made aware of their rights** on the processing of the personal data as per the GDPR and the relevant and executive national legislation (particularly the rights to access, rectify and delete the personal data and their right to lodge a complaint with the relevant Competent Authority) and if yes, by what demonstrable means (e.g. the informed consent form as per above or as per other Templates, attached herein?)

N/A

8. Even if anonymized or pseudonymized or aggregated data are referred to, does the dataset contain **location data** that could potentially (even via the combined use of other datasets) be **traced back to individuals**? If yes, what specific measures are taken to ensure this data (i) is anonymized or pseudonymized and (ii) cannot be used to track individuals without their consent? If no, what is the scientific methodology used to collect and gather said data?

N/A

9. In the context of risk assessment, prediction and forecasting, as foreseen in the scope of the EMERALDS project, during traffic, population movement monitoring or weather events, **is there any risk** that personal data could be inadvertently revealed in the event of an **emergency or unusual event**, because of the dataset usage, either on its own or combined with other openly available datasets, triggering identification or unwanted disclosure of PII? What measures are in place to protect - still identifiable if the dataset allows such extraction - **personal data** in these circumstances?

NO

10. For the use case of Trip Characteristics Inference as per the EMERALDS project scope, are there specific measures to ensure that **inferences made about trip characteristics** cannot be linked back to **specific individuals** or reveal **sensitive information** about their **habits or routines** i.e. by identifying specific individuals' absence or presence routines whether in the home or in a professional environment or in other premises?

N/A

11. Are there any potentially personal identifiable information (PII) in the datasets, **disclosable**

by combination with other datasets, either open data or proprietary (e.g., E-tickets validation data)? If yes, how is PII adequately anonymized or pseudonymized or how other datasets that by combination may result in unwanted or illegal disclosures or identification before any processing takes place?

NO

B. DATA SECURITY

1. Have proportionate security measures been undertaken for protection of the data, taking into account project requirements and the nature of the data?

- If yes, brief description of such measures (including physical-world measures, if any)
- If yes, is there a data breach notification policy in place within your organization (including an Incident Response Plan to such a breach)?

N/A

2. Given the **large-scale nature** of some datasets, are there specific measures in place to protect **included personal data** at scale at the data source or in the possession of data processors?

N/A

3. Regardless of personal data, in the case of Multi-modal integrated traffic management as defined under the EMERALDS scope, are there specific measures in place to ensure **the availability and integrity of data spanning multiple modes of transport** from being disclosed in other manners than the ones intended and covered under an open data scheme?

N/A

4. Are there specific measures in place to secure **sensitive infrastructure data**, if present?

N/A

C. DATA TRANSFERS

1. Are personal data transfers beyond project partners going to take place for this deliverable?

NO

- If “yes”, do these include transfers to third (non-EU) countries and if what policies apply?

2. Are personal data transfers to public authorities going to take place for this deliverable?

NO

3. Do any state authorities have direct or indirect access to personal data processed for this deliverable?

NO

3. Taking into account that the Project Coordinator is the “controller” of the processing and that all other project partners involved in this deliverable are “processors” within the same contexts, are there any other personal data processing roles further attributed to any third parties for this deliverable? And if any, are they conformed to the GDPR provisions?

NO

4. Given the geographical diversity of the datasets, are there measures in place to ensure compliance with specific personal data protection regulations **in different jurisdictions** i.e. at the place of the data source establishment as well as at the place of the establishment of a Data processor?

N/A

5. Are there additional protocols for data transfers involving **sensitive infrastructure data**, if present?

NO

D. ETHICS AND RELATED ISSUES

1. Are personal data of children going to be processed for this deliverable (ie. “underage” signified e-tickets)?

NO

2. Is **profiling** of identifiable individuals in any way enabled or facilitated for this deliverable?

NO

3. Are **automated decisions** for identifiable individuals made or enabled on the basis this deliverable?

NO

4. Have partners for this deliverable taken into consideration system architectures of **privacy by design** and/or **privacy by default**, as appropriate?

YES

5. Have partners for this deliverable taken into consideration gender equality policies or is there an explicit reasoning that dismisses such risk as unsubstantiated or such need as irrelevant as per the methodology of work and production of the deliverable?

YES

6. Have partners for this deliverable taken into consideration means of protecting the confidentiality of the dataset if it is not signified as open data?

N/A

7. Are there additional considerations around the collection and processing of **location data** and data **that could potentially be used to infer patterns about individuals' movements**?

NO

8. Have partners identified any **additional ethical issues** related to the processing of sensitive infrastructure data?

NO

9. Are shared economy (ie. "Uber" transfer services or "Lime" Scooters or other solution) or other shared mobility infrastructures used by the data sources? If yes, are there measures in place to ensure that the processing of **shared mobility data** respects privacy rights?

NO

10. In the context of Traffic Flow Data Analytics, are there specific considerations to ensure that the **analysis of traffic flow data** does not infringe on privacy rights or reveal sensitive information about individuals' movements or routines?

N/A

11. Is the Project taking into account the need for an all people-inclusive policy in the future within its overall goals and not only the "tech-savvy" (i.e. elderly people not familiar with some tech devices, people with no access to tech) and does it entail possible proposals for that?

N/A

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